

EXPERIMENTS ON THE SYNTHESIS OF FURANO COMPOUNDS.
PART VI. SELF-CONDENSATION OF *iso*COUMARANONE

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A synthesis of 2-phenylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid is described. Self-condensation of *isocoumaranone* affords 3-*o*-hydroxyphenylacetylcoumaranone-2. It is shown that Pfeiffer and Enders' 2-methylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid is really 3-acetylcoumaranone-2. 3-Acetyl-, 3-propionyl- and 3-benzoyl-*isocoumaranone* can be prepared by the action of respective acid anhydride and the corresponding sodium salt on *isocoumaranone*.

In the synthesis* of 1:2 benzodiphenylene oxide, recently found in the coal tar distillation products by Kruber and Oberkobusch (*Chem. Ber.*, 1951, 84, 831), 2-phenylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid (I) was a suitable starting material. The present communication reports the synthesis of this acid. The exploration of alternative methods, as set forth below, has furnished interesting results.

It was hoped that the isomeric compound 3-benzoylcoumaranone-2 (II), if synthetically available, would under appropriate conditions be transformed into the acid (I). A synthesis of (II) was attempted therefore by the action of ethyl benzoate on *isocoumaranone*. In the presence of metallic sodium, dry sodium ethoxide or better sodium hydride, a reaction took place yielding a product, $C_{18}H_{12}O_4$, and the ester was recovered unchanged. As the product is also formed if ethyl benzoate is omitted in the above experiments, its formation must be as a result of self-condensation (dimerisation) of *isocoumaranone* ($C_9H_6O_2$). This is particularly interesting as the self-condensation of coumaranone and its derivatives have been observed long ago and the constitution of the products elucidated (Fries and Pfaffendorf, *Ber.*, 1910, 43, 212; 1911, 44, 114; Baker and Banks, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 279).

The product is ketonic and acidic in character. It readily furnishes a copper chelate, $C_{18}H_{12}O_4Cu$, and shows a deep blue ferric reaction. With one mole of diazomethane, a monomethyl ether is obtained. This ether shows no ferric reaction and it is still a phenol as it affords an acetyl derivative. With acetic anhydride, the compound furnishes a diacetyl derivative. On these grounds, there is little doubt that the self-condensation product of *isocoumaranone* should be represented as (III). Ethyl α -*o*-hydroxyphenyl-acetoacetate (IV), obtained by the self-condensation of ethyl *o*-hydroxyphenylacetate in the presence of sodium ethoxide, was also found to have similar properties as (III). The probable mechanism of formation of (III) is as follows:

* The synthesis will be communicated later.

Although (III) affords a diacetyl derivative, as mentioned above, a deep-seated change takes place if sodium acetate is used along with acetic anhydride. This product, m.p. $119-20^\circ$, is also obtained from the diacetyl derivative by the further action of acetic anhydride and sodium acetate. The compound analysed as $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_4$ and contained one acetyl group. On hydrolysis, a compound, $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$, m.p. 135° , was obtained which behaved in a similar manner as (III). For example, the compound is acidic; it furnishes an oxime and a dinitrophenylhydrazone; it readily affords a copper chelate, and shows a deep blue ferric reaction. The compound $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$ must therefore be 3-acetylcoumaranone-2 (V). This was confirmed by the synthesis of its acetyl derivative (VI), m.p. $119-20^\circ$, from isocoumaranone, acetic anhydride and sodium acetate. It was soon discovered that a product of m.p. $135-36^\circ$, obtained by Pfeiffer and Enders (*Chem. Ber.*, 1951, 84, 247) by the action of acetic anhydride on *o*-hydroxyphenylacetic acid in pyridine and alleged to be 2-methylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid (VII), is identical with the compound, $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_3$, obtained above. Pfeiffer and Enders' product is therefore (V) and its methyl ester described by them is really the methyl ether (enol). The so-called anhydride (VIII), m.p. $118-19^\circ$, obtained by them by the action of acetic anhydride and sodium acetate on *o*-hydroxyphenylacetic acid, was identified as (VI).

*iso*Coumaranone was also acylated with propionic anhydride and sodium propionate, yielding 3-propionylcoumaranone-2. 3-Benzoylcoumaranone-2 (II) was similarly prepared, employing benzoic anhydride and sodium benzoate.

Although it has not yet been proved feasible to convert (II) into the acid (I), this was obtained in the following manner:

The keto-nitrile (IX), obtained from *o*-hydroxyphenylacetone nitrile (Robertson *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 420; Offe and Jatzkewitz, *Chem. Ber.*, 1947, 80, 469) and ethyl benzoate, readily cyclised in the presence of acid into 3-cyano-2-phenylcoumarone (X). On mild alkaline hydrolysis (X) afforded the related amide; the acid (I) was, however, obtained along with benzoic acid under drastic conditions. The latter arises by the fission of the furan ring. The synthesis was confirmed by the decarboxylation of (I) to 2-phenylcoumarone.

It remains to be mentioned that on boiling (III) or (IV) with hydrochloric acid in acetic acid, an isomeric non-ketonic phenolic acid is obtained.

The compound affords an anhydride (lactone) with propionic anhydride. Two structures, (XI) and (XII), are possible for this compound. Of these (XI) appears more likely but a decision between the two can only be made after accumulation of further data.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Attempted Condensation of Ethyl Benzoate with isoCoumaranone: Self-condensation of isoCoumaranone.—A cooled mixture of isocoumaranone (0.54 g.), ethyl benzoate (0.7 g.) in anhydrous thiophene-free benzene (15 c.c.) was treated with sodium hydride (0.12 g.). A vigorous evolution of hydrogen took place immediately and colorless sodium salt began to separate. After refluxing for 1 hour on the water-bath with the exclusion of moisture, the mixture was cooled, decomposed with ice water and the alkaline layer acidified carefully. The gum which separated easily solidified. This was collected (0.52 g.) and crystallised from acetic acid in colorless needles, m.p. 156-57°. The product, 3-o-hydroxyphenylacetyl coumaranone-2 (III) is very soluble in sodium bicarbonate, develops a deep blue coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride and a deep violet-purple colour with sulphuric acid, gradually turning from light violet to bluish green. (Found: C, 71.5, 71.6, 71.6; H, 4.5, 4.6, 4.5. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 71.6; H, 4.5 per cent).

The same product is obtained if ethyl benzoate is omitted in the above preparation and if metallic sodium, dry sodium ethoxide or sodium methoxide be employed.

The *copper chelate* was prepared by the action of copper sulphate to the aqueous alcoholic solution of (III) and was obtained as a dull grey crystalline precipitate. (Found in a dried specimen: Cu, 10.5. $C_{14}H_{12}O_4Cu$ requires Cu, 10.6 per cent). As the copper complex is found to be fairly stable in acid solutions, the compound (III) promises to be a useful analytical reagent for copper.

The *oxime* was prepared by adding hydroxylamine hydrochloride to a solution of the compound in sodium bicarbonate and leaving the mixture for 48 hours, followed by careful acidification with hydrochloric acid. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 185-86° (decomp.). (Found: N, 5.0. $C_{14}H_{13}O_4N$ requires N, 5.0 per cent).

If the oxime is prepared in pyridine, it forms a compound with pyridine, crystallising from alcohol in colorless prisms, m.p. 155-56° (decomp.). (Found: C, 70.1; H, 5.3; N, 7.7, 7.7. $C_{14}H_{13}O_4N.C_5H_5N$ requires C, 69.6; H, 5.0; N, 7.7 per cent).

*All m.p.s are uncorrected.

The same compound is also obtained if the above mentioned oxime is crystallised from alcoholic pyridine. On heating the compound emits a smell of pyridine. The compound is soluble in sodium hydroxide and shows a bluish green ferric reaction.

With one mole of diazomethane, the enolic *monomethyl ether* was readily obtained from (III), crystallising from methanol in colorless needles, m.p. 134°. (Found: C, 71.9; H, 5.2. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 72.3; H, 5.0 per cent). The compound is soluble in sodium hydroxide and shows no ferric reaction. The *acetate* of this enolic ether was obtained by boiling it with acetic anhydride for 2 hours. It crystallises from alcohol in colorless prisms or leaflets, m.p. 120-21°. (Found: C, 70.4, 70.5; H, 4.9, 5.2; COMe, 13.8. $C_{18}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 70.4; H, 4.9; 1COMe, 13.2 per cent).

The *diacetate* of (III) was obtained by boiling with acetic anhydride for 2 hours. The compound crystallised from alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 131°. (Found: C, 68.3; H, 4.7; 2COMe, 24.2. $C_{20}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 68.2; H, 4.6; 2COMe, 24.4 per cent). It is insoluble in dilute alkali and shows no ferric reaction. With sulphuric acid it develops a similar colour reaction as (III).

Self-condensation of Ethyl o-Hydroxyphenylacetate (cf. McElvain and Roberts, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 2007).—The ester (3.6 g., prepared according to Ofe and Jatzkewitz, *loc. cit.*) in dry benzene (15 c.c.) was refluxed for 6 hours with anhydrous sodium ethoxide from sodium (1.0 g.). The mixture was decomposed with ice water and the product isolated from the aqueous layer as usual. *Ethyl xy-di(o-hydroxyphenyl)-acetoacetate* (IV) crystallised from acetic acid or benzene in colorless prismatic needles, m.p. 147-48° [mixed m.p. with (III) was 140°]. (Found: C, 68.3; H, 5.7. $C_{18}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 68.9; H, 5.7 per cent). The compound is soluble in sodium bicarbonate, affords a copper chelate and shows a deep blue ferric reaction. With sulphuric acid a similar colour reaction as (III) is given.

The self-condensation could not be brought about by isopropylmagnesium bromide which was reported to be particularly successful with ethyl phenylacetate (Conant and Blatt, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 51, 1227).

Action of Acetic Anhydride and Sodium Acetate on 3-o-Hydroxyphenylacetyl-coumaranone-2 (III).—The compound (1.0 g.) was boiled for 1½ hours with acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) and sodium acetate (fused, 1.0 g.). The *product* (VI) (0.65 g.) crystallised from alcohol in pinkish mica-like plates, m.p. 119-20° which developed a bluish coloration with sulphuric acid. (Found: C, 66.0, 66.2; H, 4.6, 4.7; COMe, 21.0. $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 66.0; H, 4.6; 1COMe, 19.7 per cent). (Pfeiffer and Enders, *loc. cit.*, report C, 65.16, 64.96; H, 4.88, 4.62 for the same compound, m.p. 118-19°; mixed m.p. 119-20°).

Hydrolysis of the Product.—The acetyl compound (0.5 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (5 c.c.) and refluxed with concentrated hydrochloric acid (0.5 c.c.) for ½ hour. On dilution with water colorless leaflets of 3-*acetylcoumaranone-2* appeared, crystallising from dilute alcohol in colorless needles, m.p. 135°, undepressed on admixture with Pfeiffer and Enders' so-called 2-methylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid, m.p. 135-36°. The compound is volatile in steam and develops a deep blue ferric reaction.

With sulphuric acid it produces a blue colour and readily affords a copper chelate with copper sulphate. (Found: C, 68.1; H, 4.6. $C_{10}H_8O_2$ requires C, 68.3; H, 4.6 per cent). The *oxime*, prepared in sodium bicarbonate solution, crystallised from dilute alcohol in colorless leaflets, m.p. 156° (decomp.)*. (Found: N, 6.9. $C_{10}H_8O_2N$ requires N, 7.3 per cent). The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* crystallised from a large volume of acetic acid in orange-red plates, m.p. 238° (decomp.). (Found: N, 15.2. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6N_4$ requires N, 15.7 per cent).

Action of Acetic Anhydride and Sodium Acetate on isoCoumaranone.—*isoCoumaranone* (1.0 g.) was boiled with acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) and sodium acetate (0.5 g.) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The product (VI) crystallised from alcohol in pinkish plates, m.p. $119-20^\circ$, identical with the product mentioned above; yield 0.65 g.

3-Propionylcoumaranone-2: (a) *From o-Hydroxyphenylacetic Acid.*—A solution of *o*-hydroxyphenylacetic acid (3.0 g.) and propionic anhydride (7.8 c.c.) in pyridine (40 c.c.) was heated on the water-bath for 4 hours. The mixture was cooled, acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid and the crystalline matter that separated was collected after 24 hours. The product was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate, clarified by norit and acidified. Bluish white crystals of *3-propionylcoumaranone-2* (0.5 g.) appeared, crystallising from dilute methanol in bluish leaflets, m.p. $98-99^\circ$. (Found: C, 69.6; H, 5.3. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 69.5; H, 5.3 per cent). The compound shows a deep blue ferric reaction and affords a copper chelate with copper sulphate. The enolic *methyl ether* was prepared by diazomethane and crystallised from dilute methanol in colorless needles, m.p. 101° , showing no ferric reaction. (Found: C, 70.7; H, 6.0. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 70.6; H, 6.0 per cent).

(b) *From isoCoumaranone.*—This was done by boiling *isocoumaranone* (0.5 g.) with propionic anhydride (5 c.c.) and sodium propionate (0.3 g.). The gummy product obtained by addition of water was extracted with sodium bicarbonate, filtered and acidified to provide a poor yield of the propionyl derivative, m.p. and mixed m.p. 99° .

3-Benzoylcoumaranone-2 (II).—A mixture of *isocoumaranone* (1.0 g.); benzoic anhydride (5 g.) and dry sodium benzoate (1.2 g.) was heated for 3 hours in vacuum at $170^\circ-180^\circ$ (cf. Allan and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 2192). The semi-solid mass was taken up in benzene and shaken for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour with a solution of sodium carbonate (80 c.c., 10%). The aqueous layer was clarified with norit and acidified. Benzoic acid mixed with a bluish green mass appeared. The mixture was collected and then warmed with water (150 c.c.) till benzoic acid dissolved, leaving an oil. The mixture was cooled under the tap till the oil solidified and then collected quickly. *3-Benzoylcoumaranone-2* (II) was obtained as greenish lumps (0.6 g.), crystallising from aqueous alcohol in greenish leaflets, m.p. 100° . On sublimation this was obtained in cream-coloured needles, m.p. 100° . The compound is soluble in bicarbonates and gives a deep blue ferric reaction. It readily affords a copper chelate and with sulphuric acid produces a yellowish green solution rapidly, changing from green to blue. (Found: C, 76.0; H, 4.6. $C_{15}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 75.6; H, 4.2 per cent). The enolic *methyl ether* crystallised from aqueous methanol in colorless prisms, m.p. 108° . (Found: C, 75.8; H, 4.9. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 76.2; H, 4.7 per cent).

* On keeping, the sample decomposed completely.

2-Phenylcoumarone-3-carboxylic Acid (I).—A mixture of *o*-hydroxyphenylacetone nitrile (0.7 g.) (Robertson, *loc. cit.*) and ethyl benzoate (0.8 g.) in thiophene-free benzene (12 c.c.) was added to dry sodium ethoxide (from sodium, 0.24 g.), refluxed for 6 hours and left overnight. On working up the *keto-nitrile* (IX) was isolated (0.4 g.), crystallising in colorless prisms from ethyl acetate-light petroleum, m.p. 160-66° (with previous sintering due to cyclisation). (Found: N, 5.6. $C_{15}H_{11}O_2N$ requires N, 5.9 per cent).

Cyclisation.—The foregoing *keto-nitrile* (8.0 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (20 c.c.) and boiled for 1 minute with HCl (conc., 4 c.c.). The whole mixture was basified and *3-cyano-2-phenylcoumarone* (X) was crystallised from dilute acetic acid in colorless plates, m.p. 80-82°, yield 6.5 g. (Found: C, 82.2; H, 4.4; N, 6.4. $C_{15}H_9ON$ requires C, 82.2; H, 4.2; N, 6.4 per cent).

Hydrolysis.—The nitrile (0.4 g.) was boiled for 4 hours with aqueous alcoholic potash (10 c.c., 10%). Very soon colorless silky needles of the *amide* (X, CONH₂ in place of CN) appeared which resisted further hydrolysis due to its low solubility in alcohol. Crystallised from acetic acid, this was obtained in colorless needles, m.p. 261°. The compound can be purified by sublimation. (Found: N, 5.9. $C_{15}H_{11}O_2N$ requires N, 5.9 per cent).

If the hydrolysis is done in diethyleneglycol for 7 hours at 160°-170°, the nitrile (3.8 g.) afforded a mixture of acids which on fractional crystallisation from dilute alcohol furnished *2-phenylcoumarone-3-carboxylic acid* (1.2 g.) in colorless needles, m.p. 192-94°. (Found: C, 75.2; H, 4.0. $C_{15}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 75.5; H, 4.2 per cent). Benzoic acid (2.0 g.) was obtained from the filtrate. The *methyl ester* obtained by the action of diazomethane crystallised in prismatic needles from light petroleum, m.p. 80°. (Found: C, 75.8; H, 5.0. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 76.2; H, 4.7 per cent). Decarboxylation of the acid by heating with 5 times the weight with lime afforded *2-phenylcoumarone* as a colorless oil which quickly solidified. This crystallised from alcohol in colorless plates, m.p. 120-21° (lit. m.p. 120°) developing with sulphuric acid a greenish yellow solution, rapidly turning green. (Found: C, 86.4; H, 5.2. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{10}O$: C, 86.6; H, 5.2 per cent).

3-Acetyl-2-phenylcoumarone.—An excess of methylmagnesium iodide was added to the nitrile (X) and the mixture refluxed for 1½ hours. The dirty green complex on decomposition provided the ketone as an oil which did not solidify due to impurities. The *2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone* crystallised from acetic acid in shining red plates, m.p. 210°. (Found: N, 13.2. $C_{22}H_{16}O_5N_4$ requires N, 13.5 per cent).

Action of Hydrochloric Acid on (III): *Isomerisation*.—The compound (III) (3.0 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (40 c.c.) and boiled with HCl (conc., 10 c.c.) for 1½ hours. Water was added just to the crystallisation point and the *product* (2.4 g.) collected and crystallised from dilute acetic acid. This was obtained in colorless prisms, m.p. 194-95°, showing no ferric reaction. (Found: C, 71.6; H, 4.6. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 71.6; H, 4.5 per cent). The compound dissolves in sulphuric acid imparting a stable violet colour. If crystallised from dilute pyridine, the compound forms a complex with pyridine, m.p. 125-28°. (Found: C, 72.6; H, 4.9; N, 4.3. $C_{16}H_{12}O_4 \cdot C_5H_5N$ requires C, 72.7; H, 4.9; N, 4.0 per cent).

The crystals lose pyridine in the course of 2 months and fall to powder and the m.p. rises to 194-95°. The *methyl ester* crystallises from dilute methanol in colorless needles, m.p. 131°. (Found: C, 72.0; H, 5.0. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 72.3; H, 5.0 per cent). The *acetyl* derivative, prepared with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate, crystallises from acetic acid in colorless needles, m.p. 220°. (Found: C, 69.4; H, 4.6; -COMe, 13.9. $C_{18}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 69.6; H, 4.5; 1COMe, 14.0 per cent). The *propionyl* derivative was prepared with propionic anhydride and a trace of pyridine. It crystallised from alcohol in colorless prisms, m.p. 170°. (Found: C, 70.2; H, 5.0. $C_{18}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 70.4; H, 5.0 per cent). If pyridine is not added the sole product is an *anhydride* (lactone), crystallising from alcohol in thick plates, m.p. 138-39°. (Found: C, 77.2; H, 4.3. $C_{16}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 76.8; H, 4.0 per cent). The compound is insoluble in dilute alkali.

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